

Immaterial Desires: Cultural Integration of Experimental Digital Art

Dejan Grba

In this paper, we explore how the creative dynamics of experimental digital art (EDA) relate to mainstream contemporary art (MCA) and digital culture. We discuss artworks that combine playful creative thinking with procedural fluency and leverage complex information technologies, in order to address major cultural issues and encourage vigilance in our appreciation of the arts, society and human nature. However, the conceptual and technical sophistication, variability and technological entanglement of EDA simultaneously marginalise such practices and expose them to exploitation by MCA. This conflicted relationship exemplifies the uneasy coevolution between the open-ended diversity of artistic creativity and the ambiguous flux of discourses, criteria and hierarchies in mainstream culture, commerce and scholarship. It also indicates that EDA practices – whose poetic logic is essential for providing critical insights into our world – merit broader public awareness, requiring innovative modes of academic, educational, financial and technical support.

Introduction

The cultural integration and long-term impact of contemporary EDA are affected by its technological entanglement, by the insufficient institutional support that exists for its preservation and popularisation, and also by its relationship with MCA. EDA includes a rich repertoire of practices, based upon the innovative or unconventional exploration of emerging digital technologies (often in correlation with scientific research), which continuously redefine the notions of traditional and new, thus challenging the distinctions between artistic process, experience and product. Since its origins in the early computer art of the 1960s, EDA has passed through several creative periods, which have always involved a deep engagement with information technologies and with the phenomenology of digital culture (Taylor, 2014). Since the early 2000s, EDA has expanded and diversified beyond purely computation-based methodologies and has been unfolding in a broad spectrum of creative endeavours, poetics and incentives, which often combine bricolage with generative methodologies (Grba, 2020, p. 64).

Generative methodologies in art are based upon intentionally interfacing predefined systems with different factors of unpredictability in preparing, producing or presenting the artwork. By approaching the artwork as a dynamic catalysing event or process inspired by curiosity, susceptible to chance and open to change, generative methodologies frequently entail bricolage. Bricolage leverages the affinity and skill for adopting tools, materials and artefacts from the immediate surroundings in order to redefine and repurpose them through analogy-making and discovery (Lévi Strauss, 1962). It is integral to EDA projects which push the envelope of methodology, production and presentation through playful, but not necessarily preordained, experimentation with ideas, tools and cultural phenomena.

Motivated by a keen awareness of their socio-technical context and exuding well-informed wit, experimental digital artists often address the phenomenology of digital culture through emblematic technological systems, such as the Internet or artificial intelligence (AI), which are becoming ubiquitous and essential, but still remain largely elusive, exclusive, opaque or misunderstood. They build their projects upon multi-layered interconnections between programming languages, libraries, application programming interfaces, software stacks, platforms and services that run on networked hardware with increasing complexity and an accelerated pace of change. In everyday life, we consider these technical layers as guaranteed invisible services, but they are unstable and unreliable as they evolve according to capricious changes in business, technology and politics (Castells, 2010).

Entanglements

A complex interrelatedness between artists' ideas, techniques and presentational modes is inherent in artmaking in principle, but the speed and volume of technological changes make it difficult for digital artists to keep their projects running when the hardware/software systems that they work with change significantly, usually within a timespan of between several months and a few years. Furthermore, contemporary digital artworks are becoming increasingly time-based, continuous, interactive, relational and dependent on various networked transactions during their production or exhibition. Many projects are created with the precise intention of engaging the social and political consequences of ephemerality, while also addressing the fragility of information technologies by emphasising their transitory

nature. This performative intricacy is essential for experiencing their poetic identity; therefore, it is difficult to preserve or recreate these works without guaranteeing the appropriate functionality of all their interdependent layers.

Having anticipated the issues of technological entanglement, some notable digital art projects were initiated as live processes or events, but finalised and exhibited in a documentary format. For example, in *Face to Facebook* (2010), Paolo Cirio and Alessandro Ludovico created a suite of software bots that harvested one million Facebook profiles, filtered out 250,000 profile photos, custom-tagged their facial expressions (relaxed, egocentric, smug, pleasant, etc.) and posted them as new profiles on a fictitious dating website called *Lovely Faces* (Cirio, 2010). *Lovely Faces* was online for five days, during which time the artists received several letters from Facebook's lawyers, eleven lawsuit warnings, and five death threats (Gleisner, 2013). Since then, the project has been exhibited as a multimedia documentary installation (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 → Paolo Cirio and Alessandro Ludovico, *Face to Facebook*, 2010. View of the exhibition *Artists as Catalysts* at the Alhóndiga Bilbao, Spain, 2013. Photo: Paolo Cirio, 2013. Courtesy of the artist.

!Mediengruppe Bitnik's *Random Darknet Shopper* (2014-2016) was a live generative project that humorously exploited web anonymity issues. It centred around a software bot which roamed the dark web marketplaces such as Agora or Alpha Bay, where it occasionally purchased items with a weekly budget of 100 USD in Bitcoins. The goods were delivered directly to the exhibition spaces, where they were displayed with a screen device monitoring the bot's shopping activities (!Mediengruppe Bitnik, 2014).

Since 2016, gallery presentations of *Random Darknet Shopper* have featured a collection of purchased goods with a screen replay of the bot's shopping and its various legal consequences (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 → !Mediengruppe Bitnik, *Random Darknet Shopper*, 2014-2016. View of the exhibition *The Darknet - From Memes to Onionland. An Exploration* at Kunst Halle St. Gallen, Switzerland, 2015. Photo: Gunnar Meier / Kunst Halle St. Gallen, 2015. Courtesy of the artists.

Many EDA projects, on the other hand, feature continuous real-time transactions between artificial or human networked agents. Our experience of such projects becomes fully meaningful once we understand their real-time filtering logic. For example, in Matthew Cherubini's installation *Afghan War Diary* (2010), the artist's web application connects to a Counter-Strike war game server, capturing in real-time the events of players being killed by other players (frags). Frags trigger a chronological search in the Wikileaks database containing over 75,000 secret US military incident reports on the war in Afghanistan. Based on the retrieved data, the website shows the geolocations of the incidents on a virtual globe in a three-channel arrangement (Cherubini, 2010) (Fig. 3).

With *The Pirate Cinema* (2012-2014), Nicolas Maigret and Brendan Howell generate a continuous supercut by live sampling the world of peer-to-peer exchange. Their installation monitors the stream of the one hundred most downloaded torrents on a popular BitTorrent tracker, captures the video and audio snippets currently being served and plays them on the multichannel screen set, with information about their origin and destination (Maigret and Howell, 2012) (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3 → Matthieu Cherubini, *Afghan War Diary*, 2010. Screenshot from: <http://awd.site.nfoservers.com/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021). Photo: Matthieu Cherubini, 2010. Courtesy of the artist.

Fig. 4 → Nicolas Maigret and Brendan Howell, *The Pirate Cinema*, 2012-2014. View of the exhibition *The Pirate Cinema* at the Centre Pompidou, Paris, 2017. Photo: Nicolas Maigret and Brendan Howell, 2017. Courtesy of the artists.

These generative arrangements can be preserved as documentation and their processes can be simulated by accessing a database with pre-recorded events, transactions and triggering instances. However, simulation cannot fully rebuild the emotional impact of the artworks, which requires our conscious involvement with the remote agents' actual deeds and their consequences. Our empathy in this seemingly ambivalent participation comes with the contextual insights emerging live from the abstraction layer of technology.

Similarly, digital artworks that involve continuous, multilateral real-time interactions between intelligent or automated actors cannot be adequately represented through simulation. For example, in Matt Richardson's *Descriptive Camera* (2012), a photographed image generates a narrative interpretation by a remote human agent. When we point the *Descriptive Camera* at a subject and press the shutter button, the device's CCD captures the image and sends it directly to an Amazon MTurk worker tasked to write down and upload its short description, which the device then prints out (Richardson, 2012). While modern digital cameras use AI to process pictures and capture metadata, the *Descriptive Camera* deliberately requires human intellectual labour to deliver intelligent interpretation of the photographs (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 → Matt Richardson, *Descriptive Camera*, 2012. Photo: Matt Richardson. Courtesy of the artist.

Conversely, in *The Latent Future* (2017), Nao Tokui and Shoya Dozono (Qosmo) explore the expressive potentials of generative interaction between the machine learning semantic model and the human or machine-created news material. *The Latent Future* features a deep learning system trained on a collection of past news texts, which continuously captures Twitter newsfeeds and uses their discerned meanings to create fictional news (Tokui, 2017). The news is presented in a 3D model, which maps each sentence's high-dimensional "latent feature" vectors, while the spatial distances between the sentences correspond to their relative semantic differences (Fig. 6). This work is informed in real-time by the largely unpredictable dynamics of the Twitter galaxy and by Twitter's filtering algorithm, which represents many important aspects of current socio-political trends.

Fig. 6 → Nao Tokui and Shoya Dozono (Qosmo), *The Latent Future*, 2017. View of the exhibition *Open Space 2017: Re-envisioning the Future* at the NTT InterCommunication Center, Tokyo, Japan, 2017. Photo: Kioku Keizo / NTT InterCommunication Center, 2017. Courtesy of the gallery.

In Jonas Eltes' installation *Lost in Computation* (2017), all agents are artificial. It continuously generates a real-time conversation between a Swedish-speaking chatbot and an Italian-speaking chatbot, connected through the Google Translate service (Fig. 7). It simultaneously highlights the ambiguities of machine cognition and showcases the increasing accuracy and flexibility of language modelling algorithms (Eltes, 2017). The key poetic features in all these works emerge through our uncanny awareness of the here and now being continuously rearticulated through heterogeneous, dislocated and concurrent human-machine interactions.

Fig. 7 → Jonas Eltes, *Lost in Computation*, 2017. View of the installation as part of the *Arte Laguna* event at Fabbrica, Treviso, Italy 2018. Photo: Jonas Eltes / Fabbrica, 2018. Courtesy of the artist.

Mnemonics

The first wave of institutional responses to EDA's techno-cultural challenges had involved projects for the systematic curation, archiving, preservation and representation of digital art. It was pioneered throughout the 1990s by organisations and online initiatives such as the Centre for Art and Media in Karlsruhe (ZKM), the Museum of Modern Art in New York, the ISEA Symposium Archives, the Ars Electronica Archive, the SIGGRAPH Digital Art Show Archive, the Archive of Digital Art (ADA), or the Digital Art Museum (DAM), among others. They had been dealing both with the technological dynamics of the twentieth century and with the issues of digital art's broad perception as being less material and more participatory, process-based, temporal or transitory than traditional fine arts (Gere, 2004; Fino-Radin, 2016). They helped develop a new understanding of the museum as a cultural institution, established new curatorial models and artist collaboration protocols, and also defined new strategies for representation and audience engagement (Paul, 2008).

Faced with the questions of technological impermanency, obsolescence and the varying degrees of long-term material support, they outlined the technological workflows of digital art museology based on keeping the original hardware operational, continuously updating the software and developing the emulators for running archived artworks on modern hardware. Although a number of early computer artworks had been lost, some were restored through retro-computing (Wigley, 2014), while many others had been stored as a programme code that can be run in modern environments, or rendered with modern hardware. Some can be formally interpreted and reconstructed even without a source code by reverse-engineering the original imagery, for example in projects such as Matthew Epler's *ReCode* (2012), Joachim Wedekind's *Digital Art Gallery* (2014) and Martin Zeilinger's *Pattern Recognition* (2017). However, viewed from that perspective of digital art museology, most of the artworks described in this paper cannot be fully integrated and properly preserved. They facilitate complex relational experiences of socio-technical entanglement, which can be emulated only hypothetically by sophisticated AI systems trained to imitate the behaviour of human and machine agents.

Within this context, the rising popularity of AI art and crypto art has refreshed and expanded potentially promising layers of digital culture, such as virtual

museums/galleries, online exhibitions, collections and marketplaces.¹ Notwithstanding their current momentum, it is uncertain how resilient and useful these platforms will be in serving as mid-to long-term EDA archives, because most of them were neither designed nor intended for such purposes. They have been increasingly incorporated into the world of MCA, whose selection criteria, operations and discourses are substantially market-driven (Stallabrass, 2006; Shanken, 2016), so that its interest in AI art and crypto art is guided more by the commercial authority of AI and blockchain than by the need to problematise and reimagine our relationship with digital technologies.

Exploits

Since the early computer art in the 1960s, EDA has had an ambiguous relationship with MCA and, despite a few intermittent hypes, remains both marginalised and occasionally exploited by it (Bishop, 2012; Taylor, 2014). With the growing ideological authority and socio-economic power of AI, MCA has been appropriating the AI phenomenology, and its handling of AI art has morphed from its association with post-digital art² in the past decade. Post-digital artists thematise the effects of digital culture by taking digital technologies as common utilities, and mainly produce their works in conventional materials and non-interactive media (Paul, 2015). This approach conforms to MCA's imperatives for tradeable materiality, but sacrifices the intricate tension between the artworks' conceptual, expressive or narrative layers and the contextual logic of the media technologies in which they appear. Abiding by the post-digital formula, artists such as Hito Steyerl, Trevor Paglen, Pierre Huyghe or Lucy McRae present their AI works in marketable forms of installation, sculpture, video and photography.

Experimental AI artists also seek the career advantages of organised institutional support, which tempts them to compromise some of the defining features of their artmaking in order to accommodate MCA's requirements for scarcity, commercial viability and ownership. Christie's sale of the *Portrait of Edmond de Belamy*, created by the Paris-based collective Obvious in 2018, is a widely discussed example (Epstein et al, 2020). It showcased MCA's hijacking of the popular misinterpretations of AI in order to sensationalise AI art by

1 Such as AIArtists.org, AI Art Gallery, Creative AI Lab, Nifty Gateway, OpenSea, Rarible and others.

2 Sometimes also called post-media art or post-Internet art.

de-emphasising human agency in the creative process, as well as by promoting the ever 'blurring line between artist and machine' (Elgammal, 2018; Notaro, 2020). By presenting the "algorithms" as artists (Schwab, 2018; Browne, 2020, pp. 7-9), MCA disregards scientific knowledge about the limited creative autonomy of AI systems, thereby dismissing well-informed notions about the complex relationship between artistic creativity and technology (O'Hear, 1995; Boden, 2004; Hertzmann, 2018; Grba, 2020, pp. 75-77). Several artworks deftly expose the side effects of MCA's flirting with AI. For example, Disnovation.org's *Predictive Art Bot* (since 2017) (Fig. 8) is a chatbot which relentlessly generates concepts for art projects based on current art discourse and occasionally proposes absurd future trajectories for art on its own website (<http://predictiveartbot.com>) and Twitter (Maigret and Roszkowska 2017).

Fig. 8 → Disnovation.org (Nicolas Maigret and Maria Roszkowska), *Predictive Art Bot V3*, 2017. View of the installation at the *Mapping Festival*, Geneva, Switzerland, 2017. Photo: Gabriel Asper / CC NC-SA 4.0, 2017. Courtesy of Disnovation.org.

Competent experimental AI artists are well aware of the subtleties of AI technology and often explore them directly in their projects, so they would be expected to show reluctance in acceding to MCA's "streamlining" of AI art. However, soon after Christie's sale of the *Portrait of Edmond de Belamy*, Sotheby's chose Mario Klingemann's *Memories of Passersby I* (2018) for their AI art debut. Although Klingeman's work is both technically and formally more sophisticated than the *Portrait...*, it similarly conforms to MCA's demands by imposing custom-designed material components which are conceptually, technically and aesthetically redundant. Its limited-edition set is protected by a Bitcoin-based certification of authenticity, which could be considered as a more suitable (even though in principle no less objectionable) option for enforcing the scarcity and ownership of digital artworks. Within that context,

blockchain cryptographic products such as Non-Fungible Tokens (NFT) have been readily adopted by the MCA market (Finzer, 2020; Christie's, 2021). It seems that the recent interactions between experimental AI art and MCA have been reinforcing conservative modes of expression, concepts and aesthetics, rather than making new creative incentives (Browne, 2020). AI artists' endeavours to enter MCA by complying with its market-driven canons may bear a high cost in terms of their creativity and critical edge, these being features that distinguish the most successful EDA.

Universal (instabil)ities

Nevertheless, contemporary EDA is not uniquely affected by risky creative compromises, an ambivalent cultural status and museological uncertainties. These arise from the asymmetries between human inventiveness, ethics, available technical resources, socio-political imperatives and cultural trends, which are as old as the arts themselves. Although the arts rely on complex production and presentation technologies, requiring a multifaceted contextual knowledge for a deeper understanding and appreciation, artists do not always envisage their works being either conceptually or materially future-proof. Whether they just wish to enjoy a quick expression or aim to reach the remote spatiotemporal continuum with their works, artists have to face the fact that nothing meaningful lasts forever in the entropic universe.

Demonstrating human creativity as a capacity for the rapid and unpredictable generation of highly variable and context-related alternatives (Miller, 2001), the arts are particularly prone to decay. A classic example is provided by Leonardo da Vinci's conceptual and technical experimentation, which resulted in many unfinished works and in the accelerated deterioration of his masterpieces. In that sense, the material precariousness of EDA confronts us with the ultimate impossibility of unconditionally preserving any event, process, object or other entity that carries symbolic value.

By exploring concepts such as time, death and vanity, artists have appreciated art's cultural relativity, understanding that an artwork lives and dies just as we do.³ Artworks vary not only in terms of their material resilience, but also

³ As Marcel Duchamp remarked in a 1966 interview: '[...] I believe that a picture, a work of art, lives and dies just as we do' (Baudson, 1993).

in their emotional, informational, exploratory, cognitive or political impact. They are not uniformly interesting or engaging, and their values are not fixed; therefore the obsolescence of the arts is always contextual as well as material. When an artwork requires an explanation which is too long, too complex or too difficult to understand, then it significantly loses its relevance (Quaranta, 2020). Ideally, the instability of artistic mental worth may seem to reflect scientific epistemological assets, such as critical thinking and falsification, but the reputation of artists and their works is greatly affected by fancy, fashion and the appeal of authority.

The instability of artistic values also evokes the reductive economy of conscious experience (Nørretranders, 1999), which suggests that perceptive brevity and forgetfulness may be evolutionary adaptive. Nevertheless, forgetting and decay are probably not beneficial for the evolution of human society. Cultural memory and preservation build up the civilisational infrastructure by providing efficient access to functional and well-organised accumulated information, which is essential for fostering creativity and learning, for deepening our understanding of what it means to be human, and also for improving the sense of our place in nature.

Essentials

MCA's reductive commodification of dynamic, entangled and "immaterial" avant-garde practices such as EDA may be rationalised by the immediate commercial interests, but its conservatism diminishes the overall value of (artistic) knowledge in its capacity for change. It degrades our mentality and impoverishes our cultural heritage by enforcing an arbitrary disproportion of visibility and relevance upon different artworks. MCA's capitalisation on our primitive notions of possession and ownership exploits our pragmatically constrained concepts of existence and time (Heller and Salzman, 2021), which is unethical from a broader perspective because it nourishes false intuitions about our special place in the universe, and "protects" our ignorance, hypocrisy, vanity and delusions of self-importance.

The expressive logic of EDA practices is essential for establishing deep insights into the relevant aspects of our world and society, while its cultural instability exemplifies the uneasy coevolution between the open-ended complexity of artistic inventiveness and the ambiguous flux of discourses, criteria

and hierarchies in the worlds of art, commerce and scholarship. The creative dynamics of EDA also rearticulate the intricacy and unpredictability of our ecology, economy, politics, relationships and everyday life. Less dramatically, but more sensibly and often more meaningfully than global disruptions, experimental digital artworks engage us with the fact that our notions of permanence and coherence are useful delusions, whereas uncertainty is one of the fundamental features of nature. They empower ideation and foster responsibility in assessing our moral standards and social norms, tackling the ever-changing present and anticipating possible futures. Therefore, they merit special attention in order to raise broader public awareness, which requires innovative forms of academic, educational, financial and technical support.

The strategic factors for addressing the issues, trade-offs and risks, as well as for anticipating the future requirements of EDA, are resourcefulness, sustainability, robustness, scalability, flexibility, accessibility and transparency. However, the contingent and emergent nature of experimental digital artworks indicates that their long-term preservation will often be less important than their appropriate documentation and extensive tactical presentation while all their components are still operational. These considerations imply a diversity of institutional formats, scales and approaches, which offers greater versatility, resilience and accessibility than centralisation, exclusivity, monopolistic standardisation and commercialisation (Ippolito, 2016). The optimal strategy would be to instigate, fund, connect and coordinate a multitude of platforms and projects of different scopes into a robust network for archiving, distributing, exhibiting and learning about digital art.

References

- Christie's (2021) 'Beeple's Opus'. Available at: <https://www.christies.com/features/Monumental-collage-by-Beeple-is-first-purely-digital-artwork-NFT-to-come-to-auction-11510-7.aspx> (Accessed: 24 April 2021).
- Baudson, M. (1993) 'An interview with Marcel Duchamp', edited transcript of the interview with the artist, filmed by Jean Antoine in 1966. Translated by Sue Rose. *The Art Newspaper*, 27, April.
- Bishop, C. (2012) 'Digital Divide: Contemporary Art and New Media', *Artforum*, 51(1), pp. 434–441.
- Boden, M. A. (2004) *The Creative Mind, Myths and Mechanisms*. 2nd edition. London & New York: Routledge.

- Browne, K. (2020) 'Who (or what) is an AI Artist?' [Preprint Article]. Available at: https://kieranbrowne.com/publications/who_or_what_is_an_ai_artist.pdf (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Castells, M. (2010) *The Rise of the Network Society – The Information Age: Economy, Society, and Culture, Vol. 1*. 2nd edition. Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Cherubini, M. (2010) *Afghan War Diary*. Available at: <http://awd.site.nfoservers.com/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Cirio, P. (2010) *Face to Facebook*. Available at: <https://paolocirio.net/work/face-to-facebook/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Disnovation.org (Nicolas Maigret and Maria Roszkowska) (2017) *Predictive Art Bot V3*. Available at: <http://peripheriques.free.fr/blog/index.php?/works/2017-predictive-art-bot-v3/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Elgammal, A. (2018) 'When the Line Between Machine and Artist Becomes Blurred', *The Conversation*. Available at: <https://theconversation.com/when-the-line-between-machine-and-artist-becomes-blurred-103149> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Eltes, J. (2017) *Lost in Computation*. Available at: <https://jonaselt.es/projects/lost-in-computation/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Epler, M. (2012) *ReCode*. Available at: <http://recodeproject.com/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Epstein, Z., Levine, S., Rand, D. G. and Rahwan, I. (2020) 'Who Gets Credit for AI-generated Art?' *Iscience*, 23(9), DOI: 10.1016/j.isci.2020.101515.
- Fino-Radin, B. (2016) 'The Nuts and Bolts of Handling Digital Art', in Paul, C. (ed.) *A Companion to Digital Art*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, pp. 516-536.
- Finzer, D. (2020) 'The Non-Fungible Token Bible: Everything You Need to Know About NFTs', *OpenSea*. Available at: <https://opensea.io/blog/guides/non-fungible-tokens/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Gere, C. (2004) 'New Media Art and the Gallery in the Digital Age', *Tate Research Papers*. Available at: <http://www.tate.org.uk/file/charlie-gere-new-media-art-and-gallery-digital-age> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Gleisner, J. (2013) 'Paolo Cirio's Lovely Faces', *Art 21*. Available at: <http://magazine.art21.org/2013/08/12/new-kids-on-the-block-paolo-cirios-lovely-faces/#.XMLIPKQRVPY> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Grba, D. (2020) 'Alpha Version, Delta Signature: Cognitive Aspects of Artefactual Creativity', *Journal of Science and Technology of the Arts*, 12(3), pp. 63-83. DOI: 10.34632/jsta.2020.9491
- Heller, M. and Salzman, J. (2021) *Mine!: How the Hidden Rules of Ownership Control Our Lives*. New York: Doubleday/Penguin Random House.
- Hertzmann, A. (2018) 'Can Computers Create Art?', *Arts*, 7, p. 18.
- Ippolito, J. (2016) 'Trusting Amateurs with Our Future', in Paul, C. (ed.) *A Companion to Digital Art*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, pp. 537-552.

- Klingemann, M. (2018) *Memories of Passersby I*. Available at: <https://underdestruction.com/2018/12/29/memories-of-passersby-i/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Lévi Strauss, C. (1962) *The Savage Mind*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Maigret, N. and Howell, B. (2012) *The Pirate Cinema*. Available at: <http://thepiratecinema.com/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- !Mediengruppe Bitnik (2014) *Random Darknet Shopper*. Available at: <https://www.bitnik.org/r/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Miller, G. (2001) *The Mating Mind: How Sexual Choice Shaped the Evolution of Human Nature*. New York: Anchor Books/Random House.
- Nørretranders, T. (1999) *The User Illusion: Cutting Consciousness Down to Size*. New York: Penguin.
- Notaro, A. (2020) 'State-of-the-Art: AI Through the (Artificial) Artist's Eye', *Electronic Visualisation and the Arts*, pp. 322–328. DOI: 10.14236/ewic/EVA2020.58
- O'Hear, A. (1995) 'Art and Technology: An Old Tension', *Royal Institute of Philosophy Supplement (Philosophy and Technology)*, 38, pp. 143–158. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1358246100007335>
- Paul, C. (2015) 'From Immateriality to Neomateriality: Art and the Conditions of Digital Materiality', *ISEA 2015 Proceedings*. Available at: https://isea2015.org/proceeding/submissions/ISEA2015_submission_154.pdf (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Paul, C. (ed.) (2008) *New Media in the White Cube and Beyond: Curatorial Models for Digital Art*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Quaranta, D. (2020) 'Between Hype Cycles and the Present Shock: Art at the End of the Future', *DOC#6. Nero Publications*. Available at: <https://www.neroeditions.com/docs/between-hype-cycles-and-the-present-shock/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Richardson, M. (2012) *Descriptive Camera*. Available at: <http://mattrichardson.com/Descriptive-Camera/> (Accessed: 24 April 2021).
- Schwab, K. (2018) 'An AI Learned to Make Fireworks, and They're Mesmerizing', *Fact Company*. Available at: <https://www.fastcompany.com/90156087/an-ai-learned-to-make-fireworks-and-theyre-mesmerizing> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Shanken, E. A. (2016) 'Contemporary Art and New Media: Digital Divide or Hybrid Discourse?', in Paul, C. (ed.) *A Companion to Digital Art*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, pp. 463–481.
- Stallabrass, J. (2006) *Contemporary Art: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Taylor, G. D. (2014) *When the Machine Made Art: The Troubled History of Computer Art*. New York & London: Bloomsbury Press.
- Tokui, N. (2017) *The Latent Future*. Available at: <https://naotokui.net/works/the-latent-future-2017/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).
- Wedekind, J. (2014) *Digital Art Gallery*. Available at: <http://digitalart.joachim-wedekind.de/dag/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).

Wigley, P. (2014) 'Previously Unknown Warhol Works Discovered on Floppy Disks from 1985', Carnegie Mellon University, School of Computer Science. Available at: <https://www.scs.cmu.edu/news/2014/previously-unknown-warhol-works-discovered-floppy-disks-1985> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).

Zeilinger, M. (2017) *Pattern Recognition*. Available at: <https://schloss-post.com/pattern-recognition/> (Accessed: 16 September 2021).